

Exploring optoelectronic, optical thin films, mechanical and thermal transport properties of bromide double perovskites $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ for photovoltaic and thermoelectric applications

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ABSTRACT

Lead-free double halide perovskites like $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ have demonstrated themselves potential candidates in solar cell research owing to their environmental friendliness, stability, and exceptional performance. This study comprehensively analyzes the structural, mechanical, optoelectronic and optical coating features, as well as thermodynamic and thermoelectric properties of two $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ compounds. Using the Wien2k code with GGA + mBJ exchange-correlation potentials, we confirm their structural stability in cubic phase Fm-3m and identifying them as direct band gap semiconductors ($\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$) of 0.38 eV and 1.0644 eV, respectively. Then, optical analysis reveals broad absorption bands across visible and ultraviolet wavelengths, making them suitable for photovoltaic absorbers. Finally, the thermoelectric investigations under varying temperatures show favourable properties, such as a high Seebeck coefficient with poor electronic thermal conductivity. This also yields exceptional value (0.96 and 0.994 for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$, $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively) of figure of merit (ZT) at room temperature and chemical potential $\mu-\mu_0 = -0.09\text{eV}$ near the Fermi energy level, enhancing their potential for thermoelectric applications. These findings underscore the versatility and promising future of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ as important semiconductors processing for optoelectronic, thermoelectric, and mechanical devices.

1. Introduction

To address the growing demand for clean and renewable energy, it is essential to investigate various classes of the novel materials with enhanced efficiencies, stabilities and environmental friendliness. Among them the lead based perovskites have attracted significant interest due to their diverse characteristics, including optical properties [1], photoluminescence [2,3], applications in photovoltaic technology and solar cells [4,5], high energy conversion efficiency [6,7], and thermoelectric power energy [8]. The stability and toxicity issues associated with lead have hindered the commercialization of lead-based perovskite photovoltaic devices. Therefore, in recent years, experts in this field share a

crucial goal: to elucidate the growing interest in lead-free perovskites materials known for their structural flexibility and substitutability, offering the potential to improve performance while resolving lead-related issues for useful in solar cells applications [9–11] and optoelectronic devices [12]. Since, thanks to the efforts of researchers, lead-free perovskites are now considered promising candidates among solar cell materials because of their ability to overcome problems associated with lead-based hybrid perovskites.

Double halide perovskites were introduced in 1975 by R. Haegele and colleagues when they synthesized perovskite fluorides Rb_2KFeF_6 and $\text{Rb}_2\text{NaFeF}_6$ [13]. The Halogenated double perovskites, denoted by the

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chemical formula $A_2B\dot{B}X_6$, represent an innovation within the perovskite family, where, A, B, and \dot{B} correspond to different cations and X is an anion. The double perovskites have great potential for the technological applications owing to their excellent optoelectronic properties, which includes high optical absorption and optical conductivity.

Particularly, most of these perovskites suffer from stability issues or lack in the required electronic and optical properties. Therefore, it is necessary to explore suitable combination of B and \dot{B} cations to achieve a stable material with desired electronic and optical properties. There is substantial evidence supporting the substitution of the Pb^{2+} ion of the perovskites with a monovalent B^+ and trivalent \dot{B}^{3+} cations to achieve a halide based double perovskite ($A_2B\dot{B}X_6$; $A^+ = Cs, Rb, K, Na$; $B^+ = Cu, Ag, Au, In$; $\dot{B}^{3+} = Bi, Sb, In, Ga$; $X: Cl, Br, I$) [14]. Furthermore, halide perovskites exhibit exceptional stability and offer a wider range of active light absorbers. The in-depth exploration of double perovskites, especially $Cs_2AgBiCl_6$ and $Cs_2AgBiBr_6$, contained both synthesis and comprehensive studies. The findings indicate that these compounds exhibit notable chemical stability [15]. However, both double perovskites display an extended indirect bandgap which a drawback for photovoltaic applications [16]. The available experimental and theoretical results suggest $Cs_2AgSbCl_6$ is promising candidate for the light absorbing, particularly when conjugated with TiO_2 , giving an alternative for the development of the solar cell devices out of perovskite free from lead [17]. Conversely, theoretical studies on $K_2AgBiCl_6$ and $K_2AgBiBr_6$ revealed their band gap of 2.3 eV and 1.5 eV, respectively with robust absorption in the visible range. Despite these favourable characteristics, their indirect band gap limits their use in solar cell devices [18].

Inspired by these studies, we have undertaken a theoretical investigation of the structural and mechanical stability along with elastic constants and also the optical response of the material including thin-film coating of newly developed double perovskites $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$. The thermodynamic and thermoelectric behaviours are also studied for these lead-free halide alloys. The full-potential linearized augmented wave [19,20] method based computational tool known as wien2k [21] within the framework of density functional theory [22,23] is used to perform the calculation here. The generalized gradient potential approximated by Perdew–Burke and Ernzerhof (GGA-PBE) [24] combined with the modified Becke–Johnson formalism (mBJ) [25] is used to correct effect of electron exchange correlation functional. The mBJ enables to describe the electronic properties of the semiconducting materials with precise energy band gap [26–28].

The advantages and the novelty in studying the optoelectronic, optical thin films and thermoelectric properties of lead free $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$ double perovskites, are as follows: firstly, we have extended our attention to the study of the optical characteristics of these compounds and also their thin film structures. The theoretical simulation is used to analyze the film deposition technique and their synthetic modification to vary the properties of thin films structures. We have also treated the effect of the thickness of each layer by analyzing their optical thin films spectra like Transmittance, Reflectance and Absorbance. Further we performed the influence of the substrate by using a layer on glasses substrate or freely suspended layer, the obtained results may make them as potential candidates in new thin films photovoltaic (PV) technology for single-junction and tandem PV applications. Secondly, we further present a first-principles study of thermoelectric parameters for use in thermo power energy devices.

2. Computational frameworks

We have utilized the density functional theory (DFT) [22,23] based the full-potential linearized augmented wave method [19,20] as integrated in the Wien2k code [21] to perform the computations of $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$. In the FP-LAPW method [19,20], the space is partitioned into the non-overlapping spheres with maximum possible size so-called

muffin-tins (MTs) centered at atomic sites and the interstitial region outside the MT spheres. The potentials inside the MT spheres and interstitial regions are approximated as follows

$$V(r) = \begin{cases} \sum_{\ell m} V_{\ell m}(r) Y_{\ell m}(r) & \text{Inside Muffin – Tins} \\ \sum_k V_k e^{i\mathbf{k}r} & \text{Interstitial region} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

And the basis functions are given by the following expression

$$\phi(r) = \begin{cases} \sum_{lm} [A_{lm} U_l(r) + B_{lm} \dot{U}_l(r)] Y_{lm}(r) & r < R_a \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Omega}} \sum_G C_G \text{Exp} [i(G+K)r] & r > R_a \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The coefficients $B_{\ell m}$ and $A_{\ell m}$ are determined to ensure the continuity in value and derivative of the basis functions across the muffin-tin boundary. The problem of energy dependence of the basis set that arises in linearized APW approach is corrected by including a fixed set of suitable MT radial functions U_ℓ and their energy derivatives \dot{U}_ℓ in FP-LAPW method which are the solutions of the Schrödinger equation:

$$\left\{ \frac{-d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{r^2} + V(r) - E_\ell \right\} r \dot{U}_\ell(r) = r U_\ell(r) \quad (3)$$

Similarly, the modified Becke–Johnson potential (mBJ) [25] approach consists of a Becke–Roussel potential combined to a modified version of the BJ exchange potential that can be read as:

$$v_{x,\sigma}^{TB-mBJ}(r) = c v_{x,\sigma}^{BR}(r) + (3c-2) \frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{5}{6}} \sqrt{\frac{t_\sigma(r)}{\rho_\sigma(r)}} \quad (4)$$

Where, v_{xc}^{BR} is the Becke–Roussel (BR) potential [29], designed to model the Coulomb potential created by the exchange hole, $\rho_\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^{N_\sigma} |\Psi_{i,\sigma}|^2$ is the spin- σ electron density, and t_σ is the kinetic-energy density. The parameter c in Eq. (4) is given by:

$$c = \alpha + \beta \left(\frac{1}{V_{\text{cell}}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

Here, V_{cell} is the volume of the unit cell. The experimental band gaps available for a set of materials are used to determine the parameters $\alpha = -0.012$ and $\beta = 1.023 \text{ Bohr}^{-1/2}$ using the least-squares fitting method. Since, to proceed the present simulations, the wave functions inside the atomic sphere were expanded with angular momentum $l_{\text{max}} = 10$. The expansion of the wave functions into plane waves is controlled by the plane wave cutoff in the interstitial region. This cutoff is identified through the product $R_{\text{MT}} K_{\text{max}}$, where R_{MT} is the smallest muffin-tin sphere radius and K_{max} is the magnitude of the largest wave vector. In this work $R_{\text{MT}} K_{\text{max}} = 7.5$ was used. The modified tetrahedron integration scheme was used for k-space integration. The external and internal geometries of $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$ were optimized using 1000 k-points in the irreducible Brillouin zone (IBZ) distributed according to a $(10 \times 10 \times 10)$ Monkhorst-Pack scheme [30] while the self-consistencies of the ground state energies were obtained by setting the energy convergence criteria to 10^{-4} Ry. When examining optical and thermoelectric properties, a set of 2000 k-points were used. The thin film structures are designed using the optical matrix approach as incorporated in optical thin-film design program [31,32], where a 2×2 matrix containing the layer thickness and refractive index is used to represent each layer. The transport phenomena were analysed using the semi-classical Boltzmann transport equation [33–35], implemented in the BoltzTrap code [36,37]. The elastic character of the cubic sample are estimated by using the elast code as designed by Morteza Jamal and interfaced in wien2k package [38]. Additionally, we have evaluated the temperature and pressure dependence of thermodynamic parameters for halide perovskites using the Quasi-harmonic model integrated in the Gibbs2 software program

[39–41]. The projector-augmented wave method [42] as incorporated in Vienna Ab initio simulation package (VASP) [43,44] is employed for the calculation of the energy of formation. To be consistent with Wien2K code, the PBE-GGA is used for exchange-correlation functional [24]. The energy cut-off is adopted as 400 eV.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural property and stability

A self-consistent total energy calculation was carried out for various lattice parameters of each $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ compound and the resulting energy values were subsequently subjected to interpolation through the Birch-Murnaghan equation of state [45,46], as displayed in Figs. 1 and 2, to optimize the crystal structure and derive the optimized lattice constants (a_0). Some of the double perovskites are also stable in Fm3m space group of cubic structure [47]. It's important to highlight that not all halogenated double perovskites are inherently stable compounds and hence, in the present study, the stability of the samples are verified from the octahedral factor (μ) and Goldsmith tolerance factor (t) by using Eqs. (6) and (7) [48,49]. Here, r_{Rb} , $r_{\text{B}} = (r_{\text{Ag}} + r_{(\text{In}/\text{Ga})})/2$, and r_{Br} represents the ionic radii of Rb, Ag, (Ga/In) and Br, respectively. The computed values of μ and t , fall within the range of $0.81 < t < 1.11$ [50], $0.825 < t < 1.059$ [51], and $0.41 < \mu < 0.90$ [48], which establishes the stable nature of the sample crystal in the cubic structure, ideal configuration for the double perovskites.

$$t = \frac{(r_{\text{Rb}} + r_{\text{Br}})}{\sqrt{2} * (r_{\text{B}} + r_{\text{Br}})} \quad (6)$$

$$\mu = \frac{r_{\text{B}}}{r_{\text{Br}}} \quad (7)$$

The unit cell structure of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ containing a total of 10 atoms as illustrated in Fig. 3, exhibits a distinctive feature of identical Wyckoff positions. Gourav et al. [52] recently discussed the stability of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ in detail with respect to the tolerance factor, formation energy and phonon band structure of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ where no imaginary frequencies were found throughout the entire BZ thus provide a strong base to further investigate the uncovered properties.

In DFT the formation energy plays the key role for understanding the relative stability of different atomic substitution in crystal structures. The formation energy of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ is calculated according to Equation (8):

$$H_f^{\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}/\text{InBr}_6} = E(\text{Rb}_2(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6) - 2E(\text{Rb}) - E(\text{Ag}) - E(\text{Ga}/\text{In}) - 6E(\text{Br}) \quad (8)$$

Fig. 1. Unit cell crystal structure of the perovskite structure for the two studied compounds $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{B}' = \text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$.

Fig. 2. Total energy as a function of volume fitting curve regarding $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}-\text{GaBr}_6$ crystal structure.

Fig. 3. Total energy as a function of volume fitting curve regarding $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ crystal structure.

where $E(\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6)$ is the total ground state energy of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ and $E(\text{Rb})$, $E(\text{Ag})$, $E(\text{Ga}/\text{In})$ and $E(\text{Br})$ are the total ground state energies of individual Rb, Ag, Ga/In and Br atoms in their stable configuration. The calculated negative formation energies of (-2.765 eV and -2.795 eV) of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ are in agreement with Ref. [52].

In the present samples in the $\text{A}_2\text{BB}'\text{X}_6$ model, the constituent atoms are located at the Wyckoff positions of $\text{A} = \text{Rb}$ at $8c(0.25, 0.25, 0.25)$, $\text{B} = \text{Ag}$ at $4a(0, 0, 0)$ and $\text{B}' = (\text{Ga}/\text{In})$ at $4b(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$, whereas the position of $\text{X} = \text{Br}$ is at $24e(x, 0, 0)$. Here, the position of Br in x as determined from the internal relaxation is in agreement with the experimental report of 0.25 [53]. The final output of the structural optimization yields the cubic phase of the samples with optimized lattice constants (as presented in Table 1), in close agreement with the previous

Table 1

Equilibrium structural parameters a , bulk modulus B , and its derivative B' (GPa) calculated by GGA, tolerance factor t_f , octahedral factor μ for the compounds $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$ and compared to other theoretical work values Ref ($a = [52], b = [54], c = [55]$).

Compound		$a(\text{\AA})$	$V_0(\text{\AA}^3)$	$B(\text{GPa})$	B'	t_f	μ
$Rb_2AgInBr_6$	Present work	11.0741	2291.1931	25.1464	5.1469	0.92	0.50
	Other work (a)	10.79	–	20.16	–	0.98	0.45
	Other work (c)	10.90	–	29.20	–	0.91	–
$Rb_2AgGaBr_6$	Present work	10.8214	2137.8946	27.3047	5.5122	0.94	0.45
	Other work (a)	10.76	–	22.16	–	0.98	0.44
	Other work (b)	11.77	–	29.352	–	0.91	–

theoretical values from various research studies [52,54,55].

3.2. Mechanical properties

In a cubic lattice, the elastic tensor C_{ij} is defined by the three independent elastic constants, namely C_{11} which defines the material's resistance to shear deformation, C_{12} associated with shear stress and C_{44} pertains to its resistance against shear stress. The evaluated elastic moduli C_{ij} of $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$ compounds are plotted in Fig. 4. The stability criteria ($C_{11} + 2C_{12} > 0$, $C_{11} > 0$, $C_{44} > 0$, and $C_{11}-C_{12} > 0$) established by Born-Huang's theory [56,57] is followed by the studied samples as summarized in Table 2, predicting the mechanically stable nature of $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$. Furthermore, certain elastic parameters such as bulk modulus (B), shear modulus (G), and Young's modulus (Y) also can be derived from these independent elastic tensors to understand the mechanical behaviour of the samples as given by Eqs. (8)–(20) [58–60]. The calculated high bulk modulus of $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$ suggests that these crystals possess robust structural strength. Shear modulus, which measures the stiffness of material as given by Eqs. 9–11, where, in accordance with Hills [61], G_V , G_R , and G stand for the Voigt [62], Reuss [63] and the average shear moduli, respectively. The computed values of shear modulus indicate that $Rb_2AgInBr_6$ possesses the higher shear modulus value of 10.47 GPa, signifying its greater stiffness compared to

Table 2

Elastic constants C_{11} , C_{12} , and C_{44} (in GPa), bulk modulus B (in GPa), shear modulus G (in GPa), and Young's modulus Y (in GPa), Poisson's ratio ν , Cauchy's pressure C_p (in GPa), Pugh ratio B/G , anisotropy A , Kleinman parameter (ζ), Lamé constants (λ , μ), stiffness modulus M and melting temperature T_m (in K) for $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$. Others Works Ref ($a = [52], b = [54], c = [55]$).

Elastic Parameters	$Rb_2AgGaBr_6$	$Rb_2AgInBr_6$
C_{11}	32.68 (44.12) ^a , (31.607) ^b	43.2, (37.68) ^c
C_{12}	21.83(13.81) ^a , (28.225) ^b	13.7, (11.18) ^c
C_{44}	10.49(11.17) ^a , (10.109) ^b	8.28, (9.89) ^c
$C_p = C_{12}-C_{44}$	11.4, (2.64) ^a	5.29,(1.29) ^c
B	25.45(22.16) ^a ,(29.352) ^b	23.45,(20.16) ^c
Y	21.85,(18.787) ^b	27.35
G	8.05	10.47
G_V	8.46	10.89
G_R	7.64	10.05
ν	0.36(0.393) ^b	0.31
A	1.93	0.56
B/G	3.16	2.24
T_m	746.17 \pm 300	808.36 \pm 300
μ	8.05	10.47
λ	20.08	16.46
C'	5.43	14.82
$C_{11}-C_{12}$	10.85	29.63
$C_{11}+2C_{12}$	76.34	7034
M	36.18	37.41
ξ	1.1	0.6

Fig. 4. Elastic constants C_{11} , C_{12} , and C_{44} for $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$.

$Rb_2AgGaBr_6$, which has a shear modulus of 8.05 GPa. According to Pugh's criterion, for a ductile material $B/G > 1.75$ and defines its ability to deform readily whereas below this threshold indicates its brittle nature [64]. A higher Young's modulus value corresponds to increased material strength, as determined by Eq. (13). The elevated Young's modulus value of 27.35 GPa for $Rb_2AgInBr_6$ underscores its superior strength when compared to the compound $Rb_2AgGaBr_6$, which has a Young's modulus of 21.85 GPa. The Poisson ratio calculated by Eq. (14) is anticipated to fall within the range of 0.25–0.50, with values of 0.1, 0.25, and 0.33 indicating covalent, metallic, and ionic bonding, respectively. The estimated values for sample under consideration fall within the range of 0.31–0.36 indicating their inherent nature of ionic bonding [65–67]. Cauchy pressure $C_p = C_{12} - C_{44}$ also confirm the ductile behaviour of the samples as supported by Pugh's criterion. The Zener anisotropy factor [68], which measures the dimensional stability, is defined as Eq. (15). The calculated values for $Rb_2AgGaBr_6$ and $Rb_2AgInBr_6$ are 1.93 and 0.56, respectively, which clearly demonstrate the anisotropic nature of these materials. The shear modulus C' as expressed by Eq. (16) is another essential parameter that contributes to understanding the stability of a structure. Material stability necessitates condition $C' > 0$, hence the positive values obtained for C' affirm the elastic stability of these compounds. Internal deformations within a compound can be explored through a parameter known as the Kleinman parameter (ζ) [69], which elucidates the stretching of bonds in relation to their bending, as defined by Eq. (17). A ζ value of zero signifies a reduction in bond bending, whereas a ζ value of one signifies a reduction in bond stretching. The tabulated values validate the presence of bond

stretching in these compounds. Another noteworthy mechanical parameter is the Lamé constants (λ , μ), which serve to characterize the anisotropy of a material predicated by Eqs. (17) and (18). In the case of isotropic materials, $\lambda = C_{12}$ and $\mu = C'$. The Lamé coefficients determined for $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ are provided in Table 2, corroborating the findings from the anisotropic parameter A and indicating that these materials exhibit anisotropic characteristics. In Table 2, the melting temperature for the herein studied cubic sample crystals using the C_{11} dependent Eq. (20) as proposed by Fine et al. [70] with 87 % coefficient of determination as presented. The ability of a material to withstand the deformation against a shear stress is measured by the stiffness modulus (M) given by Eq. (21). Therefore, a material with increased rigidity and enhanced resistance against deformation due to shear stress is linked to its improved M . This finding further supports the conclusion that $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ is mechanically stable and resistant to softening, making it a promising candidate for experimental preparation.

$$B = \frac{(C_{11} + 2C_{12})}{3} \quad (9)$$

$$G_v = \frac{1}{5}(C_{11} - C_{12} + 3C_{44}) \quad (10)$$

$$G_R = \frac{5(C_{11} - C_{12})C_{44}}{3(C_{11} - C_{12}) + 4C_{44}} \quad (11)$$

$$G = \frac{G_v + G_R}{2} \quad (12)$$

$$Y = \frac{9BG}{(3B + G)} \quad (13)$$

$$\nu = \frac{3B - 2G}{2(3B + G)} \quad (14)$$

$$A = \frac{2C_{44}}{C_{11} - C_{12}} \quad (15)$$

$$C = \frac{C_{11} - C_{12}}{2} \quad (16)$$

$$\xi = \frac{(C_{11} + 8C_{12})}{(7C_{11} - 2C_{12})} \quad (17)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{Y\nu}{(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)} \quad (18)$$

$$\mu = \frac{Y}{2(1 - \nu)} \quad (19)$$

$$T_m = [553 + (5.911)C_{11}] \pm 300 \quad K \quad (20)$$

$$M = \frac{(1 - \nu)Y}{(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)} \quad (21)$$

3.3. Electronic properties

We explore the electronic properties of studied materials through DFT utilizing the PBE-GGA together with mBJ methods. The energy band structure and the total and partial density of states (DOS) offer a valuable insight into the physical attributes of these materials and electronic properties. These calculations are essential for identifying the exact ground state electronic behaviour of the samples. In Figs. 5 and 6, it is evident that the highest level of valence band and the lowest level of conduction band align perfectly along the same Γ -symmetry point of the Brillouin zone (BZ) indicating that both $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ are semiconductor materials with direct energy band gap ($\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$) of 0.38 eV and 1.0644 eV, respectively, using PBE-GGA + mBJ methods,

Fig. 5. $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ band structure estimated using the mBJ + GGA calculation.

which predicts exact band gap with accurate band profile than that using only PBE-GGA approximation where we found a zero band gap for both the studied compounds respectively. Further it's worth highlighting that the estimated band gap of these two components falls within the ideal range for visible light absorption. The direct band gap natures of the materials predict the enhanced efficiency for optoelectronic applications as compared to the indirect band gap materials. The band gaps for other works have been also reported in the same range [54,55] (as listed in Table 3).

To understand the potential movement of the electrons from the valence region to conduction region and the individual contributions of the constituent elements, we performed the mBJ + GGA method to derive their total and partial DOS as plotted in Figs. 7 and 8. In these figures, the Rb states are in the deep energy level giving a negligible contribution to the electronic transitions from valence to conduction region. However, in the present hybrid model double perovskites, the contributions of the p, d -states of (In/Ga) are minor in the region close to Fermi energy level. According to Figs. 7 and 8, we observe that the highest level of valence band is constituted of Ag- d mixed with Br- p states whereas (Ga/In)- s states contribute to the lowest conduction region. Consequently, the transitions occur from the mixed valence states (Ag- d and Br- p) to the s -(Ga/In) dominated conduction region which is also accountable of the phenomena occurs in the optical response curve and thermoelectric behaviour of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ as discussed in next section.

Fig. 6. $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ band structure estimated using the mBJ + GGA calculation.

Table 3

Gap values for the two compounds $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ compared to other values (a= [54]; b= [55]).

Compound	E_g (eV)		
	Present work		Other works
	PBE-GGA	(PBE-GGA + mBJ)	Theo. (GGA + mBJ)
$\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$	0.0	0.38	1.28 ^a
$\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$	0.0	1.0644	1.32 ^b

Fig. 8. $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ densities of states (TDOS, PDOS) using the mBJ + GGA.

3.4. Electron charge density distribution

To gain deeper insights into the chemical bonding characteristics of the examined materials, we have generated charge density contour plots in the crystallographic planes (100) and (110), as depicted in Fig. 9 ($\text{B}' = \text{Ga/In}$) and ($\text{X} = \text{Br}$). Within the halide perovskite structure ($\text{A}_2\text{BB}'\text{X}_6 = \text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{In/Ga})\text{Br}_6$), a consistent observation is made regarding the ionic nature of the A-X bond, while the B-X or B'-X bonds consistently exhibit covalent characteristics, aligning with findings in existing literature [71,72]. Examining the (100) plane, the overlapping regions between Ag and Br atoms indicate the presence of covalent bonds, corresponding to AgBr_6 octahedra. Similarly, in the (110) plane, the overlapping areas between (In/Ga) and Br atoms also affirm the existence of covalent bonds, corresponding to BBr_6 octahedra. The non-overlapping and symmetrically spherical charge distributions around Rb atoms suggest ionic bonds between Rb and Br. It's crucial to note that the double halide perovskite $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga/In})\text{Br}_6$ demonstrates a mixed ionic-covalent nature, positioning it as a promising candidate for photocatalytic degradation.

3.5. Optical properties

Several domains in which the incident light interacts with the matter are interesting for their commercial use. The investigation of the response of the materials against incident photon radiation is also a powerful tool to understand its electronic properties and atomic structure [73]. This requires an analysis of essential characteristics, including the frequency dependent absorption coefficient $\alpha(\omega)$, optical conductivity $\sigma(\omega)$, complex refractive index $n(\omega)$, reflectivity $R(\omega)$, and other properties associated with the interaction of light with the double perovskites. In fact, the understanding of the complex dielectric function ($\epsilon(\omega) = \epsilon_1(\omega) + i\epsilon_2(\omega)$) also enables us to analyze these properties using different equations as mentioned in Refs. [74,75]. Since, it requires a dense mesh of K-points to estimate the accurate optical properties in the present work we have used 2000 K-points to perform the integration in the BZ. The variation of the real $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ and the imaginary $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ parts of $\epsilon(\omega)$ within the energy range of 0–26 eV of incident photon energy for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ is depicted in Figs. 10 and 11. From these figures, one can estimate the static dielectric constants as presented in Table 4, which are also in close agreement with those obtained in other theoretical studies [54,55].

The static values of $\epsilon_1(0)$ are 4.617 and 3.665 for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively. These values exhibit an upward trend as shown in Fig. 10a, reaching peaks at 5.32 arb. unit (1.56 eV) for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and 4.56 arb. Unit (2.29 eV) for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$. At resonance,

Fig. 9. Electron Density Distributions (100), (100) of $Rb_2AgB'Br_6$ (where $B' = Ga/In$) using the mBJ + GGA.

Fig. 10. Real part of dielectric function (a), refractive index $n(\omega)$ (b), reflectivity R (c) and loss (d) of $Rb_2AgInBr_6$ and $Rb_2AgGaBr_6$ compounds as functions of energy.

there is maximal dispersion of incident light energy, followed by a slight decrease as energy deviates from the resonance levels. Additionally, the dispersion of light alters with increasing energy. It is noteworthy that the substitution of Ga appears to have a more pronounced effect compared to In. Thus, the choice of cation plays a pivotal role in influencing optical applications. The refractive index $n(\omega)$ also plays a key role to determine the transparency of a system. As the incident energy increases, there is a corresponding rise in dispersion, ultimately reaching 2.148 for $Rb_2AgGaBr_6$ and 1.914 for $Rb_2AgInBr_6$, as depicted in Fig. 10b. In Fig. 11a, where the incident photon energy dependent $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ is presented, which also reflect the optical absorption and optical band gap of the alloy. Here, it is clear that up to 1.047eV and 0.30 eV, no absorption phenomena occurs for In and Ga based sample which also implies that the optical band gaps are equivalent to the electrical bandgap. The variation of extinction coefficient $k(\omega)$, which also measures the absorption of

Fig. 11. Imaginary part of dielectric function (a), extinction coefficient $k(\omega)$ (b), optical conductivity (c), and absorption coefficient (d) of $Rb_2AgInBr_6$ and $Rb_2AgGaBr_6$ compounds as functions of energy.

Table 4

Static values of the real part of the dielectric function, refractive index, and reflectivity for the compounds $Rb_2AgGaBr_6$ and $Rb_2AgInBr_6$ compared to Others studies (a= [54]; b= [55]).

	$Rb_2AgGaBr_6$		$Rb_2AgInBr_6$	
	Present work	Other work	Present work	Other work
$\epsilon_1(O)$	4.617	3.18 ^a	3.665	3.24 ^b
$n(O)$	2.148	1.78 ^a	1.914	1.80 ^b
$R(O)$	0.133	0.07 ^a	0.098	0.082 ^b

light by the matter also follow synonymous type of variation with $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ and attains it maximum values of value 11.85arb.unit and 11.71 arb. unit for $Rb_2AgGaBr_6$ and $Rb_2AgInBr_6$ at 1.25 eV and 1.26 eV, respectively. The absorption of the photon energy denoted by $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ which can be derived from $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ using the Kramer-Kronig relation [76] also

provides the insight into the optical band gap from its threshold value which can be determined by drawing a tangent in its frequency dependent curve. There are absorption peaks at approximately $167.5 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 19.8 eV for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ and peaks at $173.2 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 19.8 eV for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$, as depicted in Fig. 11d. Consequently, both $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ are well-suited for optoelectronic devices in visible and UV regions, making them particularly valuable for solar cells operating in the visible region. Reflectivity spectra ($R(\omega)$) and optical loss function ($L(\omega)$) are also significant parameters, with lower values indicating superior optical materials. $R(\omega)$ offers insights into the surface characteristics of the compounds. The calculated values of $R(\omega)$ as presented in Fig. 10d, indicates their values 0.133 arb. unit for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and 0.098 for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ at zero energy. One can note that these values increase as photon energy rises, reaching a maximum of 0.30 arb. unit (21.97eV) for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and 0.27arb.unit (20.93eV) for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$. The loss of incident photon energy due to electronic transition can be measured by the loss function [77,78]. In the $L(\omega)$ spectra of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ as presented in Fig. 10c does not reflect any reflection for the photon energy up to their energy band gap. The prominent peaks of 4.2 arb. unit and 3.5arb.unit for both $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ respectively, observed at about 22eV. As the energy levels rise, loss peaks become apparent, peaking at 3.59 arb. unit for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ at 22.9 eV and 4.27 arb. unit for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ at 22.92 eV, respectively. These materials are benefitted with their very low amplitude of reflectivity and loss function for the design of the absorption layers in the solar cells. The careful analysis of the optical conductivity spectra (σ) (Fig. 11c) suggest the maximum amplitude of σ $5899.4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $5638.9 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 9.33 eV for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively.

3.6. Optic of thin films

In the context of semiconductors and dielectrics, the predominant absorption mechanism arises from the interaction of light with electrons [79,80]. For semiconductors, there exists a minimum energy (band gap) that separates the conduction and valence regions and the transition of electrons between these two bands constitute the primary source of absorption. However, the absorption of a photon in the material occurs when its energy corresponds to the energy needed to excite an electron from allowed lower energy to another higher energy states. In the absence of energy matching between the incident photon and the required excitation energy, no excitation occurs, rendering the material

transparent to such specific radiation.

To determine the optics of the thin layers of the studied perovskites $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, we conducted this study using the optical matrix method based on the Abelès method. As a result, one can find a variety of physical approaches as well as the mathematical models to characterize the optical spectra of the thin-film structures in the literature [81–86]. In this method, a square matrix [M] as implemented in optical thin film design program [87–89] is used to design a thin layer of an absorbing material which also requires the extension coefficient and the refractive index of the material as described in section 3.5. In this process, a 2×2 matrix can be used to describe the optical response, such as transmission (T), absorption (A), and reflection (R) of each thin layer of the absorbing material. These optical responses depend on the optical constants k and n as well as the layer thickness (d). Here, the frequency dependent complex reflective index is obtained by using FP-LAPW calculations [90–95] and the obtained transmission, absorption, and reflection spectra are analysed by varying the layer thickness from 600 nm to 1300 nm for the incident wavelength of 100–1400 nm. While preparing the layer sample, two different approaches were inducted. Firstly, it was suspended on a transparent substrate (for glass $n = 1.5$, $k = 0$), and later involves a self-supporting layer (for air $n = 1$ and $k = 0$). The variation of absorbance spectra ($A\%$) as function of wavelength as shown in Fig. 12 reflects better absorbance of $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ film as compared to $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ by 85 %. Here, both the film samples prepared through layer suspended on a transparent substrate as well as free-standing layer show the spectral radiation in the visible (400 nm–800nm) to UV (200 nm–400nm) range. Further increase in the incident radiation in the infrared (IR) region, the absorbance spectra decreased rather sharply for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$. The higher values of absorbance of $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ film in the incident photon of visible to UV region make this semiconductor a suitable candidate for device fabrication of solar cell. Furthermore, one can also remark that the peaks in the absorption spectra shift towards long wave length indicating the lowering of optical energy band gap with the increase of layer thickness. Similarly, the transmittance spectra ($T\%$) of thin film structures of both the sample alloys obtained by using two estimated process of deposition (free standing layer and layer on glass substrates) and with the variation of films thickness are presented in Fig. 13. A careful analysis of the plot also reveal a comparatively low amplitude of transmittance for a wide range of electromagnetic spectrum (UV–Visible–NIR) for thicker films (for $d = 900 \text{ nm}$ and $d = 1300 \text{ nm}$) in $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$. This phenomenon

Fig. 12. Absorbance spectra of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ thin films of different thicknesses, presented for both standalone and glass-supported layers.

Fig. 13. Transmittance spectra of $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$ thin films with varying thicknesses, shown for both standalone and glass-mounted layers.

also can be regarded as the good absorbing nature of the material for solar radiation. The reflectance spectra (R%) against the wavelength for at different layer thickness 200 nm and 800 nm of $Rb_2AgGaBr_6$ and $Rb_2AgInBr_6$ thin films samples estimated using two processes of deposition are illustrated in Fig. 14. From the graphs, it could be clearly seen that at all studied thicknesses both films have poor reflectance values in the case of samples on glass substrates than the free-standing layers process. It can be concluded that this material can cause a reflection of ~20 % and 35 % of the total incident photon radiation and hence they can be used as an anti-reflection coating on the reflecting surfaces of window glasses, camera lense, video screen as well as solar cell devices to protect the cell and reduce the loss from reflection from the cell surfaces.

3.7. Thermal properties

The ab initio calculations are successful to estimate the result close to the experiments and predict the exact structure and electronic properties of the solids, however, their efficiency is limited to 0 K temperature. Hence, to overcome this limitation, we have used the Gibbs program [39–41] to study the thermodynamical properties of the sample at high pressure and temperature using Debye’s quasi-harmonic approximation [96]. In this approach, the variation of the volume of the crystal and its compressibility module (bulk modulus B_0), thermal expansion coefficient (α_V), thermal capacity and the Debye temperature at different pressure are measured with respect to temperatures from 0 to 800 K for $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$ compounds. Calculating these quantities through

Fig. 14. Reflectance spectra of $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$ thin films of different thicknesses, displayed for both standalone and glass-supported layers.

first-principles approaches represents a primary objective in the field of solid-state physics and chemistry. From Figs. 15 and 16, one can note that at a given pressure constant amplitude of volume and bulk modulus for the temperature up to 100K and beyond this temperature ($T > 100$ K) the volume of the cell also increases almost linearly whereas it is reverse in bulk modulus B_0 . On the other hand, as the pressure reduces the cell volume as well as the B_0 of the system increases with pressure at a given temperature. At room temperature and zero pressure the equilibrium volume of the unit cell and B_0 are 325.52 \AA^3 , 353.29 \AA^3 and 26.84 GPa , 21.41 GPa for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively. Similarly, knowing the significance of heat capacity parameter (C_v) to predict the thermodynamic property of a solid, here we have also studied the temperature dependence of this parameter of the sample for the different pressure as presented in Fig. 17. In Figure, the variation of C_v is proportional to T^3 following the Debye's T^3 law [96] at temperature below 200K and also depends upon the applied pressure. The magnitude of variation of C_v becomes almost linear with further increase in temperature and tends to the Dulong and Petit limit ($C_v = 248.75 \text{ J mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) for both the samples [97]. A similar variation was also observed in thermal expansion coefficient (α_v) for a given pressure (Fig. 18) for the temperature below 200K and above this temperature it again tends to linearly increase. The Debye temperature (θ_D) defines the thermal property of a solid and above this temperature the quantum effect will be dominated by the thermal vibration of the solid and the behaviour of the crystal tends towards classical effect. The estimated θ_D for different pressures as presented in Fig. 19 maintains it's almost a constant value up to 100K and starts decreasing with further increase in temperature. Furthermore, the increase in θ_D becomes visible with the pressure and its value for ambient temperature and pressure are 195.02 K and 173.34K for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively.

3.8. Thermoelectric properties

The narrow band gap semiconductors are commonly acknowledged for demonstrating a favourable thermoelectric (TE) response. Hence, the thermal transport characteristics of the samples are investigated thoroughly to unveil their TE performance using mBJ-GGA which predicts the enhanced electronic behaviour of the semiconducting sample. For the generation of green energy, the thermoelectric effect is considered as a promising technique to produce the electricity from the residual heat [98] where the Seebeck coefficient (S) measures the induced voltage due to the temperature gradient across the material. In fact, S is the one of

the major factor that predicts the high efficiency of the TE devices, as higher the S value will impose higher power factor [99]. We present the calculated thermoelectric TE properties using the semiclassical Boltzmann transport phenomenon [33–35] as employed in the BoltzTrap code [36,37]. The outcome of the calculation such as temperature dependent S , electronic part of thermal conductivity (κ_e), electrical conductivity over relaxation time (σ/τ), power factor (PF), and the figure of merit given by (ZT) which determines efficiency of the material as presented in Fig. 20. The dependence of these parameters with chemical potential (μ) in the range of -2 to 2 eV are also computed for the temperatures 100 K , 200 K , 300 K , 600 K , 900 K , and 1000 K as shown in Figs. 21–25. For an efficient TE material, it must exhibit a significantly high S and electrical conductivity to give high value of power factor but low thermal conductivity to yield high figure of merit given by $ZT = \frac{S^2\sigma T}{\kappa_e + \kappa_l}$ [100]. The absolute value of Seebeck coefficient, shown in Fig. 20a, at room temperature is $206.7 \mu\text{VK}^{-1}$ ($\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$) and $212.7 \mu\text{VK}^{-1}$ ($\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$) and then S gradually decreases with the increase in temperature. Similarly, we investigated σ/τ and that shows that both samples have almost equal amplitude of $0.6 \times 10^{19} (\Omega \text{ m s})^{-1}$ at 300 K , as shown in Fig. 20b. Moreover, we examined κ_e/τ which has almost the same value of $1.05 \times 10^{14} \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}\cdot\text{s}$ at room temperature (K) for both materials, and then, we observe that it increases gradually as one can clearly see in Fig. 20c. The lattice thermal conductivity (κ_l/τ) as a function of temperature displayed in Fig. 20d clearly show that (κ_l/τ) decreases with temperature. The value of κ_l/τ at room temperature is $1.30 \times 10^{14} \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}\cdot\text{s}$ for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ and $4.85 \times 10^{14} \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}\cdot\text{s}$ for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$. The power factor (PF) defines the efficiency of the TE conversion and is estimated as the product of the square of the S and electrical conductivity [101]. Here, we have studied the (PF) for both compounds, which has the value of $2.63 \times 10^{11} \text{ W/K}^2\cdot\text{ms}$, $2.58 \times 10^{11} \text{ W/K}^2\cdot\text{ms}$ at 300 K for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively, as shown in Fig. 20e. However, $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ has slightly larger values of PF than $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ because of its higher values of Seebeck. Additionally, at 900 K , the PF values are $5.62 \times 10^{11} \text{ W/K}^2\cdot\text{ms}$ for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ and $5.90 \times 10^{11} \text{ W/K}^2\cdot\text{ms}$ for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$. We also examined the ZT , as displayed in Fig. 20f, to assess the materials suitability for use in thermal devices. At 300 K , the ZT values for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ are 1.32 and 0.57 as indicated in Table 5. The results of the current study for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ are slightly different to those obtained for similar substances [52]. This difference is due to ignorance of the photonic part in the evaluation of ZT in Ref. [52].

Now, the analysis of the variation of thermoelectric parameters with

Fig. 15. The variation of the normalized volume with pressure and temperature for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ compounds.

Fig. 16. Changes in the bulk modulus with temperature at various pressures for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ compounds.

Fig. 17. Temperature-dependent changes in heat capacities C_V at various pressures for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ compounds.

chemical potential ($\mu-\mu_0$) ranging from -2 eV to 2 eV leads to the following observations: Fig. 21 displays that the Seebeck values decrease with increasing temperature. Their highest values are ~ 755.94 (1774.55) $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ for a chemical potential $\mu-\mu_0 = -0.05\text{eV}$ (p-type) and -511.33 (-1538.8) $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ for a chemical potential $\mu-\mu_0 = 0.05\text{eV}$ (n-type) at room temperature $T = 300\text{K}$ for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively. From the curve displayed in Fig. 22, one can estimate the maximum value of electrical conductivity for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ is $10.67(10^{20}/\Omega\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s})$ at a chemical potential $\mu-\mu_0 = -1.95\text{eV}$, and its minima is zero at $\mu-\mu_0 = 0$ within the range $[-0.50, +0.50]$ and the maximum value of $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ is $11.2(10^{20}/\Omega\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s})$ at a chemical potential $\mu-\mu_0 = -1.73\text{eV}$, and the zero conductivity at $\mu-\mu_0 = 0$ within the range $[-0.17, +0.19]$. The thermal conductivity plotted in Fig. 23 increases with increasing temperature. The power factor is a key parameter in thermoelectricity to measure the efficiency of a material to produce thermo emf from the heat. At different temperatures, the nature of variation of power factor with chemical potential can be visualized from

Fig. 24. At 900K , the power factor reaches high values of 5.91×10^{11} $\text{W}/(\text{m s K}^2)$ at $\mu-\mu_0 = -0.23\text{eV}$ for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and 5.62×10^{11} $\text{W}/(\text{m s K}^2)$ at $\mu-\mu_0 = -0.55\text{eV}$ for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$. These high-power factors indicate their efficiency to produce thermo emf making them probable candidate for thermoelectric devices. The essential parameter that the figure of merit (ZT) shown in Fig. 25 exhibits a peak value of 0.96 and 0.994 for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$, $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively at $\mu-\mu_0 = -0.09\text{eV}$ near the Fermi level and at room temperature. The high ZT values of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ make them promising candidates for thermoelectric applications. The outcome of the present study on TE properties may act as a reference for the experimental synthesis of efficient TE material.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have studied the optical response and thermal transport properties of halide double perovskites samples $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ using DFT within FP-LAPW method and the reliable TB-

Fig. 18. Temperature and pressure-dependent thermal expansion coefficient α_V of $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ compounds.

Fig. 19. Temperature dependence of the Debye temperature θ_D at various pressures of $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ compounds.

mBJ to get their precise characteristics. The analysis of the optimal tolerance factor and the elastic constants predict the thermodynamic and mechanical stability in the cubic phase. The investigation of the electronic charge density predicts the mixed ionic-covalent nature of the samples leading to a promising candidate for photocatalytic degradation. The analysis of the electronic structure also suggest that both $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ exhibit direct band gap ($\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$) semiconducting behaviour with values of 0.38 eV and 1.0644 eV, respectively suitable for optoelectronics, and within these band gap values they can be useful as new materials as part of a multi-junction devices, rather than as a single band gap solar cell. Since, in-depth investigations of the optical response spectra of the sample to the incident photons also uncover a higher order of the light absorption power with substantial optical conductivity, however low reflectivity making them promising for the photovoltaic applications. These significant spectral variations in absorbance versus wavelength with high absorption coefficient ($\alpha > 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for the studied direct band gap semiconductors $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and

$\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ also confirm their potential application as thin-film semiconductor absorbers in solar cell applications. Here, $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ and $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ films are treated by two estimated coating process, first one layer suspended on a transparent substrate and second one for free-standing layer, where the $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ compound exhibits higher absorbance of 85 % as compared to $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$ compound covering the spectral radiation from visible (400 nm–800nm) to UV (200 nm–400nm) region. The transmittance was generally found to be low for thicker films (with $d = 900 \text{ nm}$ and $d = 1300 \text{ nm}$) in $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$ compared to the other film, $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, across almost all regions of the electromagnetic spectrum (UV–Visible–NIR). Additionally, for all studied thicknesses, both films exhibited poor reflectance values when deposited on glass substrates as opposed to the free-standing layers estimated process. Moreover, a high electrical conductivity, ultra-low thermal conductivity, and a high figure of merit (ZT) value around unity ($ZT = 0.96$ and 0.994 for $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgGaBr}_6$, $\text{Rb}_2\text{AgInBr}_6$, respectively at $\mu\text{-}\mu_0 = -0.09\text{eV}$ near the Fermi level and at room temperature) which make them promising

Fig. 20. Temperature Dependence of (a) Seebeck Coefficient (S), (b) Electrical Conductivity (σ/τ), (c) electrical Thermal Conductivity (κ_e/τ), (d) lattice Thermal Conductivity (κ_l/τ), (e) Power Factor PF and (f) Figure of Merit (ZT) for $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$.

Fig. 21. Seebeck coefficient of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ computed as a function of chemical potential at different temperatures.

Fig. 22. Electrical conductivity (σ/τ) of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ as a function of chemical potential at different temperatures.

Fig. 23. Electronic thermal conductivity (κ_e) of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ versus chemical potential at different temperatures.

Fig. 24. Calculated power factor of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ versus chemical potential at different temperatures.

candidates for thermoelectric applications. We are confident that lead-free $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ perovskite materials, relying on halogens, demonstrate significant promise for applications in optoelectronics and thermoelectricity, given their impressive physical characteristics and environmentally friendly nature. These features make them highly attractive for industrial use, showcasing versatility in potential applications such as hybrid commercial Photovoltaic and Thermoelectric devices (PV/TE).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

I. Benkaddour: Software, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **A. Haddou:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Y.A. Khachai:** Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **N. Baki:**

Validation, Resources, Project administration, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **F. Chiker:** Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **H. Khachai:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation. **R. Khenata:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **N. Metadjer:** Software, Resources, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **S. Bin-Omran:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Funding acquisition. **A. Shankar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis. **Saleem A. Khan:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Data curation.

Fig. 25. Calculated (ZT) for $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ versus chemical potential at different temperatures.

Table 5

Electrical Conductivity (σ/τ), Thermal Conductivity (κ_e/τ), Seebeck Coefficient (S), Figure of Merit (ZT) and Power factor (PF) of $\text{Rb}_2\text{Ag}(\text{Ga}/\text{In})\text{Br}_6$ at Room Temperature (Other work $a = [54]$).

	Rb ₂ Ag(Ga/In)Br ₆ at 300K	
	Rb ₂ AgGaBr ₆	Rb ₂ AgInBr ₆
σ/τ ($\times 10^{19}/\Omega\text{ms}$)	0.59 (0.65) ^a	0.60 (0.45) ^a
κ_e/τ ($\times 10^{14}\text{W}/\text{mKs}$)	1.05 (1.0) ^a	1.05 (0.6) ^a
S ($\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$)	212.7 (205) ^a	206.7(175) ^a
ZT	1.32	0.57
PF ($\times 10^{11}\text{W}/\text{mK}^2\text{s}$)	2.63	2.58

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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